

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“ACROSS THE SEA, FOR MY FAMILY”

I have two children, tender and small—
One is just two, the other, seven and tall.

My work is far, across the tide,
To an island shore where dreams abide.

Each Sunday noon, my heart turns low,
For soon again, I'll have to go.
The sea between us feels so wide,
And homesick tears I cannot hide.

It's not the work that wears me thin,
But leaving home, my world within—
My wife, my kids, their warm embrace,
Left behind in our quiet place.

Aboard the boat, I feel the ache,
Thinking of smiles I'll have to forsake.
It's lonely, yes—but I endure,
For my children's future, bright and sure.

I dream one day we'll live as one,
Beneath the same roof, beneath the sun.
No more goodbyes, no parting sigh—
Just love and laughter, you and I.